

Research Methods in Data Collection Using Special Focus

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524610>*

Abstract

Data can be also be obtained from secondary sources for example, company records or archives, government publications, industry analyses offered by the media, websites, the internet and so on in some cases, the environment or particular settings and events may themselves be sources of data. Individuals provide information when interviewed, administered questionnaires, or observed. Group depth interviewes, or focus people, are another rich source of primary data.

Keywords: *Focus groups, video conferencing, panels, static and dynamic panels, the delphi technique, unobtrusive measures, special data collection methods.*

Focus Groups

Focus groups consist typically of eight to ten members with a moderator leading the discussions for about two hours on a particular topic, concept or product. Members are generally chosen on the basis of their expertise in the topic on which information is sought. Computer specialists may be selected to form a focus group to discuss matters related to computers and computing, and women with children may compose a focus group to identify how organizations can help working mothers.

The focus sessions are aimed at obtaining respondents impressions, interpretations and opinions as the members talk about the event, concept, product or service. The moderator plays a vital role in steering the discussions in a manner that draws out the information sought and keeps the members on track.

Focus groups discussions on a specific topic at a particular location and at a specified time provide the opportunity for a flexible, free flowing format for the members. The unstructured and spontaneous responses are expected to reflect the genuine opinions, ideas and feelings of the members about topic under discussion. Focus groups are relatively inexpensive and can provide fairly dependable data within a short time frame.

Introduction

The selection of and role played by the moderator are critical. The moderator introduces the topic, observes, and takes notes and /or tapes the discussions. The moderator never becomes an integral part of the discussions, but merely steers the group persuasively to obtain all the relevant information, and helps the group members to get through any impasse the might occur. The moderator also ensures that all members participate in the discussion and that no member dominates the group. Someone from the research team may also observe the proceedings through a one-way mirror, listening to the verbal statements and noticing the non verbal cues of the members.

Data obtained through these homogeneous group members are less expensive than those obtained through the various other data collection methods, and also lend themselves for quick analysis, the content analysis of the data so obtained provide only qualitative and not quantitative information. Also since the members are not selected scientifically to reflect the opinions of the population.

Focus Groups are used for

1. Exploratory studies
2. Making generalizations based on the information generated by them.
3. Conducting sample surveys.

Videoconferencing

If the regional variations in responses are expected, several focus groups could be formed including trained moderators at different locations. This process is easily facilitated through video conferencing. By zooming in on a particular member, the nonverbal cues and gestures of that individual can be captured as and when desired. This also obviates the need for an observer looking through a one way mirror. With a great strides made in technological advancement, and with the facility for communication with the moderator by relaying instant messages, video conferencing as a means of gathering information from different groups in distant locations is indeed a promising prospect for the future. It should be noted that online focus groups are also common. E-mail, websites, and internet chat rooms facilitate focus group sessions as well.

Panels

Panels like focus groups are another source of primary information for research purposes whereas focus groups meet for a one-time group session, panels (of members) meet more than once. In cases where the effects of certain interventions or changes are to be studied over a period of time, panel studies are very useful. This can be taken as the response that could be expected of consumers if, in fact they had been exposed to the advertisement. A few months later, the product manager might think of introducing a change to the flavor of the same product and might explore its effects on this panel. A continuing set of experts serves as the sample base or the sounding board for assessing the effects of change. Such expert members compose the panel and research that uses them is called panel study.

The audiometers are connected to a central computer which records when the set is turned on and spotlights what channel is turned. From these data, Nielsen develops estimates of the number and percentage of all TV households viewing a given TV show. Other panels used in marketing research include the national purchase diary panel, the national family opinion panel, and the consumer mail panel.

Bias due to mortality. The advantages and disadvantages of the dynamic panel are the reverse of those discussed for the static panel.

In sum, a panel is a source of direct information. Panels may be static or dynamic, and are typically used when several aspects of a product are to be studied from time to time.

The Delphi Technique

The Delphi Technique is a forecasting method that uses a cautiously selected panel of experts in a systematic, interactive manner. These experts answer questionnaires in two or more rounds. In the first round they are asked to answer a series of questions on the likelihood of a future scenario or any other issue about which there is unsure or incomplete knowledge. The contributions from all the experts are then collected, summarized, and fed back in the form of a second-round questionnaire. After reviewing the first-round results, the experts assess the same issue once more, taking the opinions of other experts into account. This process goes on until it is stopped by the researcher. The rationale behind this iterative process is that it eventually may lead to a consensus about the issue that is being investigated. The identity of participants is usually not revealed, even after the completion of the final report. This should prevent some experts from dominating others, allow experts to unreservedly express their opinions, and encourage experts to admit mistakes, if any, by revising their earlier judgments. The Delphi Technique has been widely used for long-run business forecasting.

Unobtrusive Measures

Unobtrusive measures or trace measures as they are also called, originate from a primary source that does not involve people. One example is the wear and tear of journals in a university library, which offers a good indication of their popularity, frequency of use, or both. The number of different brands of soft drink cans found in trash bags also provides a measure of their consumption levels. Signatures on checks exposed to ultraviolet rays could indicate the extent of forgery and fraud; actuarial records are good sources for collecting data on the births, marriages, and deaths in a community; company records disclose a lot of personal information about employees, the level of company efficiency, and other data as well. Thus, these unobtrusive sources of data and their use are also important in research.

Special Data Collection Methods

Data can be collected in a variety of ways, in different settings field or lab and from different sources, as we have just discussed. Data collection methods include interviews-face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, computer-assisted interviews. And interviews through the electronic media questionnaires that are either personally administered, sent through the mail, or electronically administered; observation of individuals and events with or without videotaping or audio motivational techniques such as projective tests. Recording, and a variety of other

Interviewing, administering questionnaires, and observing people and phenomena are the three main data collection methods in survey research. Projective tests and other motivational techniques are also sometimes used to tap variables. In such cases, respondents are usually asked to write a story, complete a sentence, or offer their reactions to ambiguous cues such as inkblots or unlabeled pictures. It is assumed that the respondents project into the responses their own thoughts, feelings, attitudes, and expectations, all of which can be trained psychologists.

The choice of data collection method depends on the facilities available, the degree of accuracy required, the expertise of the researcher, the time span of the study, and other costs and resources associated with and available for data gathering.

Conclusion

Modern technology is increasingly playing a key role in shaping data collection methods. Computer-assisted surveys, which help with both the interviewing process and with preparing and administering questionnaires electronically, are on the increase. Computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI), interactive electronic telephonic surveys, as well as administering questionnaires through electronic mail (e-mail), are now being used to facilitate data gathering.

Some of the software available for questionnaire design, response data entry, data analysis, and web and e-mail surveys are SumQuest or SQ Survey Software, Professional Quest, and the choice of data collection method depends on the facilities available, the degree of accuracy required, the expertise of the researcher, the time span of the study, and other costs and resources associated with and available for data gathering. We will now examine the various data collection methods. Perseus.

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